

Using collaborative methodology and communication for redefining and assessing new attention and inclusion strategies for forcible displaced people

Finding suitable strategies for the inclusion of forcible displaced people is a challenge for the communities hosting migrants, especially in the current increasingly complex geopolitical, sanitary and climate crisis situation where armed conflicts, ethnical and religious discrimination, sexual harassment and political opinions, among other reasons, force millions of people to flee from their home countries and regions. Tailoring these strategies in the host countries is often complex and requires a correct analysis of the forced migrants' need, and an understanding of how the personal situation of each migrant is tangled with the above mentioned conditions. Forced migration can only be understood taking into account the contexts (economic, social, legislative, political, personal) that make migrants vulnerable.

The current presentation describes how an international consortium formed by Mediterranean, Northern, Central European and Middle Eastern countries worked together with forcibly displaced people, aid organizations and other relevant stakeholders in studying, designing and evaluating 8 pilots of tailored attention and inclusion strategies for forcibly displaced people, known with the acronym of TAIS. In the first phase of the project, an extensive field study with more than 178 interviews to forcibly displaced persons was carried out in Spain, Italy, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan and Lebanon, contributing to the knowledge of forced migrants' particular difficulties, vulnerability contexts and needs in the participating countries.

Afterwards, the intensive co-creation work of the so called 'Action Research Units' in the 7 participating countries – formed by academics, experts, refugees, NGOs, policy makers, researchers and even some representatives from the business world – resulted in 8 pilot strategies for inclusion. Altogether, more than 100 workshops and meetings were held in 7 countries along the 3 years project, including 3 international cross-analysis workshops where the process and results of the integration strategies were shared and assessed. Inclusive and transparent communication was a key success driver for informing about and executing these pilot experiences, and putting together the inputs and efforts of more than 320 stakeholders. Refugee aid organizations got highly engaged in the project and contributed with their first-hand field experience and strategic proficiency to all the phases of the project.

The focus of the paper is describing the integration strategies and the communication efforts related to them, as well as sharing the methodology and results of an innovative and inclusive evaluation system of the outcomes. The extent to which these tailored strategies will be adapted and replicated in similar vulnerable contexts remains an open question, but still, several NGOs and humanitarian agencies, as well as organisations working on a daily basis with local communities, have showed their interest in the

working methodology. The continuity of the project action is also envisioned, and a new observatory on forced migration will be presented to the conference participants.

BORRADOR